

Evaluation of true ζ -potential from Electro-osmotic data of fine particles of Solid whose surface layer acts as a semiconductor

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It has been pointed out that at the solid/liquid interface, conditions are favourable for the formation of a thin semiconducting layer of solid.

Assuming the existence of such a layer its effect on electro-osmosis has been analysed.

It has been shown that the equation connecting true and apparent ζ -potentials denoted by ζ and ζ_a respectively should have the following form, for a diaphragm made of fine particles, each of radius R and filled with a dilute solution of bulk specific conductivity k ,

$$\zeta = \zeta_a \left[1 + \frac{1}{kR} (\alpha x_d + \frac{3V_s x_s}{V_l \gamma \beta}) \right]$$

In the aforesaid equation, α , β and γ are constants, x_d and x_s are the specific surface conductances of the diffuse double layer and the semiconducting layer and V_s and V_l are the volumes of the solid and solution per unit length of the diaphragm.

For a capillary of radius r the aforesaid equation assumes the form

$$\zeta = \zeta_a \left[1 + \frac{2}{kr} (x_d + x_s) \right]$$

It has been pointed out that in those cases where a thin semiconducting layer of solid is present at the solid/liquid interface, the well-known equation connecting streaming potential, E , electro-osmotic flow, V and the ζ -potential should be expressed as—

$$\frac{E}{P} = \frac{V}{i} = \frac{D\zeta}{4\pi\eta kf} \frac{i_f}{i_s + i_f}$$

where $i = (i_s + i_f)$ i_s and i_f represent the currents flowing through the semiconducting layer and the liquid respectively and kr , the specific conductivity of the solution inside the diaphragm or capillary tube as the case may be.

In treating surface conductance in electrokinetics most authors^{1,2,3} except Henry⁴ and Booth⁵, attribute its origin to the electrical double layer round the particles bathed in a dilute solution of an electrolyte in water. It is, however, quite probable that a thin layer of the order of a few atomic diameters close to the surface of the solid particles acquires the properties of a semiconductor owing to prevalence of vacant lattice sites, adsorbed impurities, non-stoichiometry and other contributory factors.

1. M. Smoluchowski, — *Handbuch der Elektrizität und des Magnetismus* (Ed. Gracia), 1921, 11, 385.
2. J. J. Bickerman, — *Z. Physik Chem.*, 1933, 163, 378.
3. F. Urbain, H. L. White and E. A. Strassner, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, 39, 311.
4. D. C. Henry, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1948, 44, 1021.
5. F. Booth, *ibid.*, 1948, 44, 955.

In the treatment of surface conductance, therefore, the effect of such a thin conducting layer close to the surface of the solid particles should be taken into consideration, besides that due to the electrical double layer extending some distance into the solution (Gouy⁶).

Diaphragm consisting of fine particles whose surface layer acts as a semiconductor: Let us suppose that very small spherical solid particles, each of radius R , are packed closely and uniformly to form a diaphragm DD , 1 cm in length and 1 cm² in cross-sectional area in a glass tube AB and the system is filled with a very dilute solution of KCl (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1

Since the particles are very small and uniformly packed, the total cross-sectional A_r of the solution at every plane such as p_1 , p_2 , etc. of the diaphragm will be the same although the cross-sectional area of the individual pores varies from point to point along such a plane. Similarly the total surface area[†] A_s of all the solid particles at every plane such as p_1 , p_2 , etc. will also be the same.

It is assumed that the solid in the diaphragm is continuous and so also is the liquid.

The electrical double layer consists of the charged surface of the solid and an equivalent charge of opposite sign in the side of the solution. According to Stern⁷ and Mukherjee⁸ this equivalent charge of opposite sign is made up of two parts: (1) a fixed part at a distance of a few ionic diameters from the charged surface of the solid and (2) a diffuse part (Gouy⁶) extending into the solution to a small depth.

According to Bickerman² only the diffuse part of the double layer contributes to surface conductance. While Urban, White and Strassner³ hold the view that the ions in the fixed part of the double layer also move, produce electro-osmotic flow and thus make their specific contribution to surface conductance.

It may be pointed out, however, that to account for the difference, between the electrokinetic potential ζ and the Nernst or electrochemical potential Φ_0 , as observed by Freundlich and Ettisch⁹, it is necessary to assume that a steep fall of potential occurs within the

[†]Suppose r_1 to be the radius of the cross-sectional area of the i th particle at some point in the plane p_1 . Then $A_{r1} = \sum 2\pi r_1$ for all the particles through which the plane p_1 passes $= \sum 2\pi r_1$ for all the particles through which the plane p_2 passes.

6. G. Gouy, *J. Phys.*, 1910, 9, 457.

7. O. Stern, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1924, 29, 506.

8. J. N. Mukherjee, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1921, 16, 321.

9. H. Freundlich and G. Ettisch, *Z. Physik. Chem.*, 1928, 115, 401.

fixed layer and that there is no electro-osmotic flow of the liquid molecules which may have penetrated into this layer. The fixed part of the double layer thus behaves as if it is a part of the solid and in this article it has been treated as such.

It is, therefore, assumed as has been done by Bickerman^a that only the diffuse part of the double layer contributes to surface conductance by the movement of ions and electro-osmotic flow.

It is further assumed, as stated already, that for the particles under consideration there exists at the surface of the solid a very thin layer, including the fixed part of the double layer, which acts as a semiconductor and contributes to surface conductance, the mechanism being different from that in the diffuse part of the double layer.

Suppose an electric field is applied through two perforated platinum electrodes FF placed near the two ends, of the diaphragm bathed in a very dilute solution of KCl (shown in Fig. 1). In the steady state a current i_s will pass through the semiconducting layer of the solid particles (which form a continuous structure) and a current i_f will pass through the solution filling the pores.

If E be the difference of potential between the two ends of the diaphragm then the following equations should hold good†;

$$i_s = \frac{(E-e)A_s x_s}{L_s} \text{ and } i_f = \frac{E A_f k_f}{L_f} \quad \dots (1)$$

where e is the back E.M.F., x_s , the specific surface conductance per unit area of the thin semiconducting layer of solid, k_f , the specific conductivity of the solution inside the pores and L_s and L_f are the lengths of the paths traversed by the currents i_s and i_f respectively.

Since the current i_s is small, the back E.M.F. e , will be small and can be neglected in comparison with E which is quite large. Again L_s/L_f will be very nearly equal to unity because the current i_s will have to pass through the thin layer of solid close to the surface of the spherical particles and i_f will have to go round the same particles embedded in the liquid.

It is reasonable to assume that inside the diaphragm there is no flow of current from the solid to the liquid or vice versa across the electrical double layer i.e., perpendicular to the interface. The potential of the double layer or the decomposition voltage will act as an effective barrier against such a flow. It is also to be noted that the effects of the double layer to the entry of i_s into the thin semiconducting layer and its exit from it will mutually cancel each other at the two ends of the diaphragm.

$$\text{Therefore, } \frac{i_s}{i_f} = \frac{(E-e)A_s x_s}{L_s} \bigg/ \frac{E A_f k_f}{L_f} = \frac{A_s x_s}{A_f k_f} \beta \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{where } \beta = \frac{(E-e)}{E} \cdot \frac{L_f}{L_s} = 1 \text{ nearly, for reasons stated already.}$$

† If σ is the specific conductivity of the semiconducting layer and Δ_s its thickness then $x_s = \sigma \Delta_s$ ($L_s \Delta_s \rightarrow 0$)

The true electrokinetic potential ζ of the particles measured by the electro-osmotic method is to be found from the equation;

$$\zeta = \frac{4\pi\eta U}{DV} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where η is the viscosity, U , the velocity, of electro-osmotic flow and D , the dielectric constant of the solution and V , the potential gradient of the applied electric field in the solution.

Since $V = \frac{i_f}{A_f k_f}$, therefore, equation (3) can be written as;

$$\zeta = \frac{4\pi\eta U A_f k_f}{D i_f} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Experimentally it is much easier to determine the bulk specific conductivity k of the solution than k_f . In actual practice $i = (i_s + i_f)$ and k are measured. Therefore, equation (4) is to be expressed as follows:—

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta &= \frac{4\pi\eta U A_f k}{D i} \frac{k_f}{k} \frac{i_s + i_f}{i_f} \\ &= \zeta_s \left(1 + \frac{i_s}{i_f}\right) \frac{k_f}{k} \quad \dots \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where } \zeta_s = \frac{4\pi\eta U A_f k}{D i}$$

In equation (5) k_f can be put equal to $k(1 + 2x_d/kr)$ where x_d is the specific surface conductance due to the diffuse part of the double layer and r the radius of the capillary which according to Ghosh *et al.*¹⁰ should satisfy the condition

$$\pi r^2 (k_f - k) = 2\pi r x_d$$

substituting the values of i_s/i_f and k_f in equation (5) the following expression is obtained

$$\zeta = \zeta_s \left(1 + \frac{A_s x_s}{A_f k} \beta + \frac{2x_d}{k r}\right) \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Since the diaphragm is 1 sq. cm. in area and 1 cm. in length $A_f \times l = V_f$, the volume of the solution inside the diaphragm and $A_s \times l = n 4\pi R^2 \gamma$ where n is the total number of spherical particles in the diaphragm and γ is a factor* by which $4\pi R^2$ is multiplied to get the effective surface. Again $n 4\pi R^2 = 3V_s/R$ where V_s is the total volume of the n particles. As has been shown by Ghosh *et al.*,¹¹ r may be replaced by R/b where b is a constant and R is the radius of a particle provided V_s/V_f is maintained constant.

10. B. N. Ghosh, B. K. Chowdhury and P. K. De, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1954, 50, 955.

11. B. N. Ghosh, S. C. Rakshit and D. K. Chatteraj, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 30, 60.

*It has been shown in a recent communication (this journal) that $\gamma = 1/3$

Introducing these values of A_s , A_f and r in equation (5) it can be written as follows

$$\zeta = \zeta_s \left[1 + \frac{1}{kr} (\alpha x_d + \gamma \frac{3V_s \beta x_s}{V_f}) \right] \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where $\alpha = 2b = a$ constant.

It follows from equation (7) that the effects of the diffuse double layer and the thin semiconducting layer on the surface conductance of the particles are additive. When the concentration of the electrolyte is maintained constant (ζ , k , x_d and x_s remain constant and if the phase volume ratio is also maintained constant, the equation (7) can be expressed as

$$\frac{1}{\zeta_s} = \frac{1}{\zeta} + \frac{m}{R} \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

where m is a constant.

Equation (8) has been subjected to experimental test by Ghosh *et al.*^{12,13} under conditions in which R is varied but the specific conductivity k of the solution and the phase volume ratio V_s/V_f have been maintained constant. The equation has been found to hold good since a plot of $1/\zeta_s$ against $1/R$ was found to be linear for all the systems so far investigated. It should be noted, however, that such investigations do not give any idea of the individual values of the terms αx_d and $\gamma 3V_s \beta x_s/V_f$.

Capillary whose inner surface layer acts as a Semiconductor:

Information on this point can be obtained from data on electro-osmosis in which uniform capillaries have been used. For a uniform capillary of unit length and radius r , the term β in equation (6) is equal to unity and A_s and A_f are $2\pi(r + \Delta r)$ and πr^2 respectively, where Δr is the thickness of the semiconducting layer and very small compared to r . Substituting these values of A_s and A_f in equation (6) and putting $\Delta r/r = 0$ finally, the following equation is obtained.

$$\zeta = \zeta_s \left[1 + \frac{2}{kr} (x_d + x_s) \right] \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

Wijga¹³ has carried out streaming potential measurements using pyrex capillary tubes and has determined the total values of $(x_d + x_s)$ at different concentrations of a few electrolytes. He has also calculated the values of x_d , the contribution of the diffuse double layer, using an equation derived on the basis of Gouy's theory of diffuse double layer. The results for KCl only are recorded below:

TABLE I
Electrolyte KCl.

Concentration $C \times 10^6$ equiv. per litre.	$x_d \times 10^6$ calculated	$(x_d + x_s) \times 10^6$ observed	$x_s \times 10^6$	Ratio $\frac{x_s}{x_d}$
1	0.077	0.7	0.62	8.1
2	0.103	0.75	0.65	6.3
5	0.157	0.83	0.69	4.4
10	0.206	1.0	0.79	3.8
20	0.263	1.3	1.04	4.0
50	0.357	2.1	1.74	4.9
100	0.462	3.2	2.74	5.9
200	0.575	5.0	4.43	7.7

12. B. N. Ghosh, S. P. Moulik and Sengupta, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1965, 9, 372.

13. P.W.O. Wijga, Thesis, Utrecht, 1946, p. 53-56.

It will be noticed from the data recorded above that the calculated values of x_d is much less than that of $(x_d + x_s)$ found experimentally. In column 4 of the table are recorded the values of x_s obtained from $(x_d + x_s) - x_d$ and in column 5, the ratio of x_s/x_d . It will be noticed that at the lowest concentration used value of x_s is about 8 times that of x_d . The ratio of x_s/x_d passes through a minimum and then increases again. Even when the ratio is minimum, x_s is about 4 times x_d . From these results it may be concluded that the contribution of the semiconducting layer to surface conductance is much greater than that of the diffuse double layer.

Diaphragm consisting of particles whose material is a semiconductor:

O'Connor, Street and Buchanan¹⁴ have found quite high values for the ratio of the observed surface conductance to that calculated on the basis of the theory of diffuse double layer for the minerals, Rutile, Cassiterite and Haematite. Therefore, they have concluded that these minerals possess semiconducting properties.

For such materials the true electrokinetic potential ζ can be found from electro-osmotic or streaming potential measurements by adapting equation (6) to the conditions of the experiments. For semiconducting particles, A_s , in equation (6) should represent the total cross-sectional area of the particles at each of the planes p_1, p_2 etc. Therefore, for unit length of the diaphragm $A_s \times 1 = V_s$ and $A_f \times 1 = V_f$. x_s in equation (6) should represent the specific conductance of the material of the particles. Hence equation (6) should be written as follows:—

$$\zeta = \zeta_s \left[1 + \frac{2x_d}{rk} + \beta \frac{V_s}{V_f} \frac{x_s}{k} \right] \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

It may be pointed out that in such cases, $x_d \ll x_s$ and the term involving it may be dropped. Equation (10) will then reduce to the form

$$\zeta = \zeta_s \left[1 + \frac{\beta V_s}{V_f k} x_s \right] \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

If the experimental conditions are so arranged that k is kept constant, while the ratio V_s/V_f only is altered, then the relation between $1/\zeta_s$ and V_s/V_f will be linear. The intercept of the straight line on $1/\zeta_s$ axis will give $1/\zeta$ from which ζ can be easily found.

It may also be noted from the aforesaid discussion that when a thin semiconducting layer of solid is present at the solid/liquid interface the following well-known relation¹⁵

$$\frac{E}{P} = \frac{V}{i} = \frac{D\zeta}{4\pi\eta k} \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

between streaming potential, E , electro-osmotic flow, V , of liquid and ζ -potential, should be written as

$$\frac{E}{P} = \frac{V}{i} = \frac{D\zeta}{4\pi\eta k_f} \left(\frac{i_f}{i_s + i_f} \right) \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

14. D. J. O'Connor, N. Street and A. S. Buchanan, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1954, 7, 245.

15. *Colloid Science*—Edited by Kravt, 1952, Vol. 1, p. 206.

where $i = (i_s + i_f)$, i_s represents the current flowing through the semiconducting layer, i_f the current through the solution and k_f the specific conductivity of the solution inside the diaphragm.

The author takes this opportunity to express his grateful thanks to the authorities of the University Grants Commission for admitting him into the scheme of "Retired Teachers" which enabled him to continue his research work.

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Received, May 18, 1967.